

Assessment of verbal features

Speaker on the left

Proficiency level (holistic score)

A1 A2 B1 B2 C1 C2

Range

A1 A2 B1 B2 C1 C2

Accuracy

A1 A2 B1 B2 C1 C2

Fluency

A1 A2 B1 B2 C1 C2

Pronunciation

A1 A2 B1 B2 C1 C2

Interaction

A1 A2 B1 B2 C1 C2

Additional comments

Speaker on the right

Proficiency level (holistic score)

A1 A2 B1 B2 C1 C2

Range

A1 A2 B1 B2 C1 C2

Accuracy

A1 A2 B1 B2 C1 C2

Fluency

A1 A2 B1 B2 C1 C2

Pronunciation

A1 A2 B1 B2 C1 C2

Interaction

A1 A2 B1 B2 C1 C2

Additional comments

Options in the drop-down menu:
+ supported interaction
- hindered interaction
0 neutral effect
? not sure

Assessment of nonverbal features

Which feature did you pay attention to?

Speaker on the left

Facial expressions (e.g., smiling, raising the eyebrows)

[drop-down menu]

Eye contact

[drop-down menu]

Head movements

[drop-down menu]

Sounds (e.g., yeah, mm, no way), laughter

[drop-down menu]

Speaker on the right

Facial expressions (e.g., smiling, raising the eyebrows)

[drop-down menu]

Eye contact

[drop-down menu]

Head movements

[drop-down menu]

Sounds (e.g., yeah, mm, no way), laughter

[drop-down menu]

Hand movements (e.g., gestures, pointing)

[drop-down menu]

Other, which?:

Additional comments (e.g. lack of a feature in the speaker on the left)

Effect of the nonverbal features on your proficiency rating

Yes No I cannot comment

Additional comments on the nonverbal features

Hand movements (e.g., gestures, pointing)

[drop-down menu]

Other, which?:

Additional comments (e.g., lack of a feature in the speaker on the right)

Effect of the nonverbal features on your proficiency rating

Yes No I cannot comment

Additional comments on the nonverbal features

Assessment of the entire dialogue (both speakers):

Your overall impression of the interaction (verbal and nonverbal interaction)

- I think the interaction worked mainly without problems
- I think there were problems in the interaction
- I cannot comment

You can expand on your answer here (e.g., turn distribution, friendliness, differences in the speakers' proficiency levels, if needed, use the speakers' IDs)